

Research Fund for Coal and Steel

Grant Agreement Number

101034041

Modelling of hydrogen activity from atmospheric corrosion in ultra-high strength steels for light structure application

AtHyCor

Deliverable D15:

Comprehensive overview of the project: State of the Art, problem, proposed approach and outcome of the project

Due date of deliverable: 01/01/2022

Actual submission date: 02/02/2022

Period covered by the Deliverable:

01/07/2021 – 31/12/2022

Start date of project: **01/07/2021**

Duration: **36 months**

Organization name of lead contractor for this deliverable:

Institut de la Corrosion - IC

1. Objectives of the project

The main scientific objective of this project is clearly to develop a simulation tool that can **model hydrogen entry and distribution into coated ultra-high strength steel (UHSS) exposed to atmospheric corrosion conditions**. The industrial aim of this project is thus to provide steel makers and car manufacturers with new data related to environmentally assisted fracture risks of ultra-high strength steels and with a simulation tool that could anticipate such risks. These main objectives can be divided into the following ones:

- A. New data for atmospheric corrosion and hydrogen entry in UHSS
 - To characterize and understand the corrosion mechanisms in simulated simplified atmospheric corrosion conditions (thin electrolyte film layer)
 - To obtain quantitative data for the corrosion processes at localized scale using an advanced combination of electrochemical and analytical techniques
 - To investigate the evolution in terms of composition, morphology and distribution of the water layer and corrosion products under atmospheric corrosion conditions
 - To simulate various aggressive environments and the respective corrosion test conditions to reveal the main difference between accelerated corrosion tests and outdoor exposures and dependence on the corrosion mechanisms

- B. New method to evaluate local hydrogen content from atmospheric corrosion
 - To quantify hydrogen entry into the steels due to atmospheric corrosion processes (galvanic coupling or free corrosion)
 - To reveal important factors that govern hydrogen generation due to atmospheric corrosion
 - To use experimental data in the simulation of simplified atmospheric corrosion processes of various coated high strength steels, considering cut edges and defects in the coating
 - To model the hydrogen entry flux due to atmospheric corrosion processes as a function of environmental conditions and coating composition
 - To tailor the model for application to more complex samples and structures
 - To build multi-physics model that links surface (corrosion activity and hydrogen entry) and bulk (stress/strain distribution and hydrogen trapping) phenomena

- C. Prediction of hydrogen assisted cracking risks under atmospheric corrosion conditions
 - To assess the risks of hydrogen assisted cracking for selected coated high strength steels under atmospheric corrosion conditions
 - To use the model to anticipate the risks of hydrogen assisted fracture under various standard automotive test conditions
 - To build a guideline for the prediction of hydrogen assisted failure of coated high strength steels under atmospheric corrosion conditions
 - To make the simulation tool available to other European research teams in order to extend the applicability of the model

2. State of the art

Design of light vehicles of the future are based on advanced high strength materials that could reduce the total car weight and consequently the energy efficiency and consumption of the vehicle [1–3]. In the case of electric cars, it could also offset the weight of power systems such as batteries and electric motors, improving the efficiency and increasing their all-electric range. Today, the competition between steels and non-ferrous alloys, such as aluminum and magnesium, is rather strong in the worldwide automotive industry [2]. To meet this challenge, steel manufacturers are developing new high-performance steel grades and particularly advanced high strength steels (AHSS) reaching now tensile strength up to 2000 MPa, as illustrated in Figure 1. Press-hardened steels (PHS) are of particular interest as the hot forming process allow high formability without strong residual stresses in the final component, compared to cold formed steels, limiting the risks of delayed fracture for instance.

Figure 1: 2021 Global Formability Diagram, Courtesy of WorldAutoSteel.

Despite the good mechanical performance of the AHSS, the steel industry still faces major challenge that is to prove that their newest steel solutions will sustain the service conditions of a vehicle, particularly those related to hydrogen assisted cracking under atmospheric corrosion conditions. Indeed, ultra-high strength steels are known to be sensitive to hydrogen embrittlement [4–7] and nowadays, from early steps, the fabrication processes are adapted to control the risks of delayed fracture for instance [8–11]. Even the microstructures of advanced steels are tailored to decrease the sensitivity of the steels to hydrogen. However, atmospheric corrosion can be an additional source of hydrogen during service life [12–17], which was probably not so dangerous for low grades, but become critical for high strength steels with ultimate tensile strength above 1000 MPa. Thus, the hydrogen assisted cracking (also called environmental assisted cracking) must be particularly considered due to the high tensile strength of such steels, which decreases drastically the critical level of hydrogen [18–21].

Due to requirements from the automotive industry, AHSS must be protected against corrosion, which is done by using Zn-based or AlSi-based coatings, adapted to the hot forming process, and completed with paint systems if necessary. However, defects in the metallic coatings after hot forming, or at cut edges (punched holes for instance), can expose the steel to the environment, activating locally the corrosion processes that can progress severely. Extensive work has been performed by the scientific community on the corrosion properties of zinc, zinc-alloy or aluminum-silicon coatings under atmospheric corrosion conditions with several progresses [22–26]. Corrosion damage under service conditions is anticipated using more or less empirical accelerated corrosion tests or outdoor exposure on standard samples. However, such tests must be limited in time to match the industrialization schedule of new concepts and designs. Consequently, stress corrosion cracking investigations of such steels under accelerated corrosion test conditions can lead to different sensitivity and ranking, which often makes the predictive

ability of the tests questionable.

The high economic impact of atmospheric corrosion can be reduced by improving the corrosion management and prevention based on predictions that are more accurate. The combination of experimental data with mathematical corrosion models is pointed out as the solution to simulate corrosion processes over short- and long-term periods, a first step to predict risks of failure under service conditions. Models of corrosion have been developed taking advantage of easy access to high calculation capacity of modern computers. Thus, the complexity of the models has increased in recent years being able to simulate complex mechanisms, such as atmospheric corrosion [27,28], which is briefly described in Figure 2. As shown, complex interactions between environment, water film and metals occur during atmospheric corrosion, which must be taken into account in models for accurate prediction of the phenomenon.

Figure 2: Atmospheric corrosion is the result of a complex interaction between metal(s) in contact with an electrolyte film. This film changes in time (1), electrode reactions (2) take place depending on a changing electrolyte composition (3) and interaction with air (4), from [27].

Corrosion under atmospheric conditions has been modelled using different types of approaches over the years [27–32]. Space- and time-dependent simulations are nowadays more common thanks to commercial software tools. The models are able to investigate species transport together with local chemical and electrochemical reactions, that are critical for understanding atmospheric corrosion [32–37]. Detailed modelling of atmospheric corrosion was used previously in the ATCORAS European project [38] for aluminium-based coated steels (AlZnMg). The aim was to develop a modelling tool for coated steels. A methodology based on conventional and advanced analysis tools was established to investigate corrosion products formation, distribution of species, local electrochemical reactions and galvanic couplings. The local mechanistic multi-ion numerical model was built from the balance equations to describe the corrosion behaviour of the AlZnMg coatings. Thus, a huge amount of experimental and numerical work was done, by the participants of the program from both academic and industrial worlds. Finally, a local model was developed for understanding atmospheric corrosion behavior of steel cut-edges protected by Al-based alloys. The model included several blocks dealing with electrochemical and chemical reactions, electrolyte thickness, surface blocking by corrosion products and non-uniformity of the coating electrochemical activity linked to selective dissolution of the phases. Using the model, both scientific and industrial findings were obtained, particularly on the dependency of corrosion products to the local electrolyte composition and pH, and on the protective ability of corrosion products from various AlZnMg alloys, allowing better design of such coatings. However, the simulation was mainly limited to constant input conditions and no cyclic tests could be simulated. Thus, additional experimental data sets and more tailored modelling developments are still necessary to build a predictive atmospheric corrosion simulation tool. To model accurately atmospheric corrosion and in a quantitative manner, experimental data are required particularly under very thin film conditions that are present during drying or wetting of surfaces for instance. Electrochemistry under thin electrolyte layers has been developed

by several authors, as summarized in [28]. Such techniques require careful sample preparation and the use of model samples and electrolytes in most of the cases to ensure the good reproducibility of the measurements. Thus, the use of industrial materials and conditions is rather challenging, and several replicates will be necessary to explain the results and characterize each test condition.

Corrosion of the steel or galvanic coupling with the protective metallic coating can be also responsible of hydrogen production at the surface of steel [12,39], which could lead to hydrogen assisted cracking phenomenon [16]. The hydrogen activity is strongly related to the environmental and surface conditions, but also influenced by the steel microstructure and the presence of stress/strain concentration defects. In the case of high strength steels, the galvanic coupling at cut edges or at the location of defects in the coating can be an important source of hydrogen [15,17]. Red rust, consequence of strong local acidification, can also enhance hydrogen activity as illustrated using the SKP technique, see Figure 3. The red rust location corresponding to active area with very low potential is a source of hydrogen that can be detected at the opposite side of the steel membrane by SKP because of interaction of permeated hydrogen with the surface and particularly iron oxides.

Figure 3: A) Photograph of the red rust developed at the steel surface contaminated with NaCl deposit. B) SKP mapping of the contaminated side, showing the active area (lowest potential) at the location of the red rust. C) SKP mapping at the opposite side of the steel membrane (non-contaminated side) showing the impact of hydrogen that diffused through the steel on the surface potential. Adapted from [15].

When hydrogen activity is low, cracks in high strength steel would start preferentially from surface defects, such as micro-cracks created by shear cut process. Increasing hydrogen activity can lead to cracking in areas with large stress and strain, as observed in cold formed components or after welding without good control of the process. In most of the cases, the cracking process initiated from the surface or sub-surface of the steel. Hydrogen activity at

the surface is linked to both internal and external hydrogen fluxes. In the one hand, external hydrogen activity is fully related to environmental conditions and corrosion processes and occurs by definition at the exposed surface of the steel. In the other hand, internal hydrogen activity is influenced by the microstructure of the steel (hydrogen trapping) [40] and stress distribution. For instance, irreversible trapping can decrease the hydrogen activity until the saturation of the traps. On contrary, reversible trapping can increase the amount of hydrogen available for the hydrogen cracking mechanism. The desorption of hydrogen from the bulk creates hydrogen flux at the surface of the steel. Hydrogen trapping energy is usually characterized by the thermal desorption spectroscopy (TDS) technique [5,41–43].

For high strength steels, crack growth rate in the presence of hydrogen is very fast, leading to rapid failure of specimens or components after build-up of the critical crack embryo. Thus, the crack initiation step is particularly of high interest when considering components formed from thin plates. Conditions of crack initiation are fully related to the local stress and hydrogen concentration. As the experimental determination to such local hydrogen concentration remains rather complicated for industrial materials, simulation methods were developed to model hydrogen distribution in a strain/stress field [44–48]. These approaches require specific sets of experimental data for each steel. However, to mimic real service conditions, the boundary conditions of such model must be fully related to the external hydrogen sources and activity, which are deeply interlinked with the atmospheric corrosion mechanisms. This specific subject is still scarcely understood and constitutes an important R&D challenge.

As a conclusion, the knowledge of local corrosion mechanisms and hydrogen fluxes at the surface of the steel is crucial to anticipate hydrogen assisted cracking and mandatory for the simulation of hydrogen embrittlement phenomena under atmospheric corrosion conditions. This project will provide key answers to fill this gap. However, the scientific obstacles to achieve this aim are numerous, both from the experimental and numerical point of view. The most critical ones were identified from the literature and the experience of the participants of the project:

- New data sets for the selected steels must be obtained at both local scale and under thin film conditions. Careful preparation and the samples and several replicates will be necessary to investigate industrial materials and representative conditions. Thus, a large effort will be dedicated to this task in the project by several partners experienced in such investigations, namely the Instituto Superior Técnico Lisboa (IST-ID), the University of Chemistry and Technology of Prague (UP) and Institut de la Corrosion (IC).
- The links between corrosion and hydrogen entry remains quite unclear. Modelling of such aspects must be based on strong experimental data that are not yet available. Hydrogen evolution reactions will be investigated under various conditions and the proportion of hydrogen produced at the surface that enters and diffuses into the steel will be revealed using advanced electrochemical permeation tests and SKP investigations under atmospheric corrosion conditions. The knowledge and experience from all the partners will be gathered to achieve this goal.
- Building a mechanistic model of atmospheric corrosion, and even more a model of hydrogen entry from atmospheric corrosion, is rather complex due to the complexity of the mechanisms and the huge quantity of influencing parameters. Thus, the experience from RISE Kimab (KIMAB) on modelling complex phenomena, and particularly atmospheric corrosion mechanisms, will be very useful. Modelling will be performed in as a first step on a very simple geometry to allow the use of a large set of variables. Then, a systematic parametric study will be performed to identify the most influencing parameters and to build a simplified model using several approximations. The deviation from the initial model will be quantified. The acceptance criteria for a simplification will be discussed and based on the knowledge of the participants and the requirements in terms of model accuracy. Finally, more complex conditions will be simulated and compared to the experimental validation data sets.
- The unified model of atmospheric corrosion, hydrogen entry and distribution in strain/stress field is particularly complex from the numerical point of view. Thanks to the experience of the partners in the use of the COMSOL Multiphysics® software, the interconnections between the different models developed in the project should be simplified. The architecture of the model will be designed to obtain mostly weak

couplings between the various blocks of the unified model, which will be based on experimental observations.

- For the validation of the models, long-term real exposure data are necessary, which will be obtained in the project using both static and dynamic (vehicle) conditions. However, monitoring corrosion activity over such a long period of time, and particularly on-vehicle, will be rather complex. Then, it is proposed to focus on the most relevant phases of the corrosion exposure and fully monitored the most active period from a corrosion aspect.
- Tests to investigate hydrogen cracking sensitivity of steels were mostly designed to rank materials. Thus, to establish criteria of hydrogen cracking, relevant mechanical loads and specimen designs must be selected. Both static tests (constant load or displacement) and dynamic tests (SSRT and incremental step load testing) will be performed during the project using samples with pre-existing defects such as the one obtained from shear cut edge or punched hole. This aspect will be particularly discussed with the Automotive industry.

3. Methods and techniques

To anticipate the risks of hydrogen assisted cracking, steel samples under stress are usually exposed to corrosive conditions, which often include standard accelerated corrosion tests or more simple conditions, and acceptance is based on non-failure/failure criteria or stress thresholds in the best case. Nevertheless, most of the accelerated corrosion tests were designed to reproduce corrosion aspects and, by essence, to accelerate the phenomena. However, the mobility of hydrogen is an important factor in the hydrogen assisted cracking mechanism, and such acceleration can lead to unforeseen failures, even in some steels grades that have been successfully used in the automotive industry for years without reported failure. More accurate predictions of the hydrogen assisted cracking phenomena are still required to allow safe use and acceptance of advanced grades in the automotive industry. Particularly, the most critical phases regarding hydrogen entry must be clearly identified. Parameters such as temperature and relative humidity, and the way how they control the corrosion rate, are of course particularly important. However, from a mechanistic point of view, the local conditions such as pH, oxygen content and local galvanic current densities must be well known and analyzed. Thus, the main objective of this project is to develop a novel methodology, based on simulation and local corrosion/hydrogen data, to reproduce accurately the corrosion degradation and hydrogen entry and propagation into steel in order to build a predictive model of hydrogen assisted cracking in steel components under atmospheric corrosion conditions.

3.1. Mechanisms of atmospheric corrosion

As a first step to anticipate the risks of environmental assisted fracture of AHSS, a better understanding of the corrosion mechanisms under complex environmental conditions is necessary. Indeed, there are still many gaps and for example new sets of relevant experimental data are missing in the case of high strength press-hardened steels coated with Zn-based or Al-Si metallic coatings that can show very different corrosion behaviors at cut edges or in pit-like defects. This project answers this need by developing a sound strategy to obtain new local corrosion data sets that will provide novel insights on corrosion mechanisms at these particular locations. Moreover, experimental data will be obtained under very thin electrolyte conditions, using for instance the SKP technique under humid conditions to control electrolyte thickness or by measuring corrosion activity, including galvanic coupling, under tailored accelerated corrosion conditions. Such data are definitely required to develop a quantitative model of atmospheric corrosion as concluded by authors of the ATCORAS project [38]. As the reproducibility of such methods is largely influenced by the sample preparation and electrolyte composition, a comprehensive and systematic study will be developed for the industrial materials. Thus, several replicates will be used for each of the investigated condition and environmental conditions will be particularly monitored to explain the deviation from one sample to another. This way, statistical analysis of the results will be possible, which should make the data even more reliable for the numerical simulation of the corrosion processes.

Coated high strength steels have been defined and supplied by ArcelorMittal (AMMR) and Voestalpine (VAS).

Samples were produced by hot forming process and the microstructure of steels and coatings will be fully representative of real automotive components, as illustrated in Figure 4. Steels and coatings will be fully characterized using well-established methods [5,49], and also advanced techniques such as FIB-SEM and FIB-TEM to investigate steel and coating microstructure and presence of defects in the coatings. For the steels, the microstructural features will be particularly investigated as potential hydrogen trapping sites. These features will be identified as reversible or irreversible trap sites from the literature data. Deformed structures will be also characterized as strong deformation can occur at cut edges. Moreover, hydrogen trapping can easily occur in plastically strained areas. The influence of the plastic deformation on the morphology of the coating and defects formation within the layer will be investigated on cross-sections.

Figure 4: Example of (left) AlSi and (right) Zn coated PHS steels, from [25,50]

The local electrochemistry and corrosion activity will be investigated using conventional and advanced techniques such as in-situ scanning vibrating electrode technique (SVET) coupled with scanning ion-selective electrode technique (SIET) and fiber-optic dissolved oxygen micro-sensor in a triple stage for quasi-simultaneous measurements, and the scanning Kelvin probe (SKP). SVET enables detection of the total ionic flow allowing identification of the anodic and cathodic areas, including spatial distribution and time evolution as the IST-team recently demonstrated [51]. Such time/spatial evolution is crucial to predict how the corrosion progresses. The location and intensity of the anodic and cathodic activity can be “quasi-simultaneously” accompanied by the monitoring of local pH thanks to SIET, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Example pH and SVET mapping on hot dip Al-Zn, from [52].

The distributions of the local pH and current density will be recorded in both horizontal (traditional) and vertical planes in order to widen the assessment of the studied corrosion process and evaluate the impact of vertical species

re-distribution. At cut edges, the time and spatial evolution of the local corrosion activity, pH gradients and dissolved oxygen evolution will be monitored to understand the protective role of the coating and its effect on hydrogen production and absorption. Total integral anodic and cathodic currents will be calculated and related to the corrosion activity. The discrepancy between values of total anodic and cathodic currents will be linked to coating thickness and composition. Local oxygen monitoring will be achieved using the fiber-optic dissolved oxygen micro-sensor. The measurements are absolutely critical as it is reported that different pH values are responsible for more or less favorable conditions for hydrogen absorption into steel and can be correlated to changes of corrosion potential [53,54].

Additionally, in the presence of artificial defects, the pH at the bottom of the defect and the in-depth variations of pH from the steel surface till the bottom, will be measured to estimate the complete range of pH across each coating or layers of corrosion products formed and to establish a correlation with the coating composition. The data will allow assessing the stability of the corrosion products formed in the defects and the occurrence of hydrogen release and absorption. The electrochemical data will be correlated to the distribution and composition of corrosion products, obtained by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) equipped with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy. Experimental data will be compared to thermodynamic diagrams build using Spana/Medusa software. The protective nature (and stability over time) of the corrosion products will be revealed.

The SKP technique will be used to assess local potential in thin film electrolyte in order to establish the true polarization of the steel and coatings under such conditions [55]. Specific samples will be designed with working (steel) and counter electrodes embedded in a non-conductive resin. The SKP probe will be used as reference electrode to measure the potential of the steel surface as a function of environmental conditions (influencing electrolyte layer thickness) and current density. Indeed, the SKP is equipped with environmental chamber to control the relative humidity in the chamber and potentiostat/galvanostat will be used to impose the current between counter and working embedded electrodes. The composition of the water film layer will be also adapted by controlling the surface concentration of salt contaminants and the pH. In a similar manner, defect-free coated steel will be investigated to quantify the evolution of the surface potential over the coating as a function of impressed current (anodic polarization) and formation of corrosion products.

The galvanic coupling will be also evaluated using SKP. In this case, the surface potential will be influenced by the corrosion products migration from the coating to the steel. The relative humidity in the SKP chamber will be controlled at different values (ranging from 50% to 95%RH) in order to reach different thicknesses of the thin electrolyte film. Volta potential and corrosion potential measurements will be performed with and without pollutants at the surface.

Additional corrosion data will be obtained at “macro” scale using accelerated corrosion tests and outdoor exposure. Galvanic coupling, corrosion rate and corrosion products will be investigated under various conditions and compared to the local data. To mimic service conditions, most of the cyclic corrosion tests used in the automotive industry are based on repeated cycles with intermittent exposure to salt contamination, relatively elevated temperature and humidity, wetting/drying phases and sometimes even freezing phases. Thus, even if good correlations have been reported compared to service conditions, the corrosion conditions are finally rather complex and extracting data related to atmospheric corrosion mechanisms using such tests could be challenging. Thus, as a first step, simplified corrosion test conditions with wet/dry cycles at constant temperature will be used to investigate these mechanisms as a function of selected environmental conditions. The corrosion products will be characterized by FTIR on these samples after defined time of exposure to evaluate the kinetic of corrosion product formation. Cross-section of the samples will be observed by SEM (using eventually FIB) and characterized using EDS.

Moreover, thickness and composition of the thin electrolyte layer will be investigated as a function of environmental conditions taking into account accumulation of corrosion products by anodic dissolution and hydrolysis processes. This will be done using a combination of techniques. The electrolyte film thickness will be estimated based on precise weighing of specimens kept at controlled relative humidity by quartz crystal microbalance. The absolute quantity of dissolved ions will be analyzed after rinsing of parallel specimens by Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) as a function of time. Insoluble corrosion products will be identified by FTIR and their quantity assessed after dissolving them in weak acid by ICP-OES.

Then, two different standard accelerated corrosion tests, namely Volvo STD423-0014 and VDA 233-102 (DIN 55635) will be used. The corrosivity will be monitored using galvanic and corrosion sensors to determine the influence of the various phases on corrosion rate and galvanic coupling evolution with time. The corrosion products will be also characterized by FTIR and SEM/EDX. For the Volvo test, slightly simpler than the VDA test, the release of metallic ions into solution will be monitored by collecting run off water under the specimens and analyzing it by ICP-OES.

Finally, outdoor and on-vehicle exposures will be also performed to gather data from real service conditions. Such data will be used in particular to improve and validate the corrosion model. The outdoor exposure is planned for a duration of 2 years, over two winter periods. The static exposure will be performed at a corrosion site owned by VAS or IC. For the vehicle exposure, a truck circulating between Göteborg and Stockholm driving approx. 150,000 km per year will be used. The corrosivity on the truck is particularly important during winter periods when extensive use of road salts occurs. As continuous monitoring of the corrosion data (galvanic coupling, instantaneous corrosion rate) is rather complicated over such a long period of time, shorter but relevant phases (for example wet periods and winter periods) will be fully monitored to gather data regarding atmospheric corrosion mechanisms. For this, atmospheric corrosion sensors will be exposed. Corrosion products obtained under each condition will be also characterized by FTIR and SEM/EDS.

3.2. Mechanisms of environmental assisted cracking

The links between corrosion and hydrogen production remain unclear in the literature especially under atmospheric corrosion conditions. Therefore, an extensive work will be performed at both local and global scales to reveal the most influencing parameters on hydrogen production and entry into coated high strength steels exposed to various corrosive conditions. In particular, the water reduction reaction and the other hydrogen evolution reactions will be quantified as a function of the climatic conditions. The cathodic reactions will be investigated as a function of local conditions of pH and dissolved oxygen. The part of cathodic current on the steel surface linked to water reduction and hydrogen production will be quantified using dedicated corrosion cell couple with integrated oxygen detector and coupled with hydrogen analyzer. Experiments will be performed under partial oxygen pressure and humidity control to vary the dissolved oxygen content in the thin film electrolyte.

The hydrogen properties in the steels will be characterized using the conventional electrochemical permeation and TDS techniques [5]. The hydrogen flux and the effective diffusion coefficient in each steel, as a function of the temperature will be evaluated using Electrochemical Permeation (EP). The trapping energies will be quantified using TDS analyses after hydrogen and/or deuterium charging of steel samples. To evaluate the impact of plastic deformation, some samples will be pre-strained prior to hydrogen charging and TDS measurement. From these investigations, a dependency of hydrogen trapping concentration to plastic deformation will be established. This approach might be necessary considering the complex straining at shear cut edges that must impact local hydrogen concentration. Additionally, samples showing shear cut edges will be investigated to evaluate the impact of the cut edges on the hydrogen trapping phenomenon. Specific thin samples will be designed for these analyses, decreasing the impact from the bulk material previously investigated.

The external hydrogen activity will be also assessed under various conditions using both the electrochemical

permeation and SKP methods and linked to corrosion activity. To limit the impact from the hydrogen trapping phenomenon, an interstitial free steel will be investigated in a first approach, with and without zinc coating. Various thicknesses will be used to extrapolate the real surface hydrogen flux from the results. Thin layer of palladium coating on the detecting side will be deposited by electro-deposition technique to improve the detection limit of the method and control the diffusion profile within the bulk. On the exposed side, large defect will be produced in the coating, increasing the steel/coating surface ratio, to facilitate hydrogen entry under atmospheric corrosion conditions.

The hydrogen activity will be then quantified for the selected high strength steels under controlled conditions using EP and taking into account the specificity of each system. Large defects will be produced in the coatings to facilitate hydrogen entry from the surface. The hydrogen activity will be evaluated as a function of the composition of the steels and the plastic deformation. The relationship between hydrogen flux, microstructure, local pH changes and mechanical parameters will be used to validate the model of hydrogen entry.

In the case of coated samples with smaller defects, the SKP technique will be applied to evaluate the local hydrogen flux under one or two rather simple conditions (constant temperature and humidity). This method is based on the evolution of the surface potential of the steel with the hydrogen outer flux from the sample. SKP measures the local electron work function that is related to the conditions (thickness, degree of oxidation) of the surface oxide. Using this technique, hydrogen can be characterized indirectly in microstructures, and the method remains semi-quantitative at the best. However, the sensitivity of the SKP is very high, and shows lateral resolution, which will be necessary to investigate small defects in the coated steel, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Potential map of the H exit side measured 7 hours after start of the exposure (a), photograph of the H entry side after the experiment (b), height profile map (c) and photograph (d) of the H entry side after corrosion products removal; corrosion pits are marked with dotted lines, from [14].

Finally, hydrogen assisted cracking tests under immersion and atmospheric corrosion conditions will be performed using both static and dynamic (slow strain rate testing – SSRT) loading modes. The influence of the hydrogen activity on the cracking phenomenon will be investigated with pre-existing defects such as the one obtained by hole punching or shear cutting. Samples will be tested under constant or incremental step load. SSRT will be used under controlled climatic conditions to assess the influence of hydrogen flux from atmospheric corrosion on the time to fracture, the tensile strength and the elongation of the samples. The geometry of the samples will be adapted to investigate the local deformability of the steel as a function of hydrogen activity. Finally, micro-tomography with high resolution (about 1 μ m) will be used ex-situ and in-situ to get deeper insight in the hydrogen embrittlement mechanism.

3.3. Modelling corrosion and hydrogen entry

All the experimental data sets will be tailored to feed 3 models: 1) Modelling of atmospheric corrosion mechanisms, 2) Modelling of hydrogen production from corrosion, 3) Modelling of hydrogen distribution in strain/stress fields. All these models will be developed in the software COMSOL Multiphysics® to allow their combination in unified model simulating both surface (corrosion activity and hydrogen production) and bulk (hydrogen distribution) phenomena in a sequential manner, as described in Figure 7. The models will be validated by additional experimental data and outdoor exposures in services conditions.

Figure 7 : Schematic representation of the architecture of the coupled model of atmospheric corrosion, hydrogen entry and hydrogen distribution in the steel.

A model that can simulate hydrogen production and entry into the steel as a function of the corrosion activity will be developed to explain and predict the severity of application conditions typical for the automotive industry, including a large set of accelerated corrosion tests.

First, a simple situation (geometric and/or layer composition) that not necessarily causes hydrogen production will be simulated. Several phenomena will be modelled within the layer and at the interphases between layer and atmosphere, and layer and solid (metal/coating) as described below.

Within the layer, species are transported:

- The transport will be modelled as fluxes caused by differences in concentration and potential (only the charged species). The liquid itself is stagnant, *i.e.* convection in the layer is neglected.
- The species fluxes will be described as taking place in a diluted solution, which means that the flux of each species is independent of the layer composition.
- Because of the diluted solution assumption, time-dependent mass balances of each species will be set up with simple species fluxes that use ordinary diffusion coefficients readily available in literature.
- The diluted solution assumption is not always realistic, especially in a water film layer that has almost dried up, so the model will incorporate activities instead of concentration. The activities will use an activity coefficient computed from the ionic strength of the liquid.
- Electroneutrality will apply everywhere within the layer, *i.e.* the sum of species charge will be zero.

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- The potential will be calculated from the conservation of charge and the current density at each point will depend on the flux and charge of all charged species.

Within the layer, homogeneous chemical reactions take place:

- The hydrolysis of metal ions, metal-chloride complexes and carbonates are typical reactions present in atmospheric corrosion.
- The model will include these as equilibrium reactions taking equilibrium constants from literature or suitable databases.

At the interphase between the layer and atmosphere the following will be included:

- Oxygen and carbon dioxide dissolution from air into the layer.
 - The aqueous concentration of oxygen in equilibrium with oxygen in air (dependent on temperature and layer composition).
 - The equilibrium aqueous concentration of carbon dioxide (dependent on temperature, and atmospheric and layer composition).
- Water evaporation and condensation driven by the relative humidity of air and layer composition affecting the thickness of the layer.

At the interphase between the layer and steel/coating surface the following will be considered:

- Electrochemical reactions
 - Oxidation/corrosion of metals
 - Reduction of oxygen
 - Reduction of protons to hydrogen gas
- Fluxes of species involved in the electrochemical reactions computed from current densities retrieved from experimental measurements (either from Tafel kinetics and/or current density vs potential).
- Precipitation of corrosion products.
 - Only the products detected experimentally will be included. The solubility products can be used to relate the fluxes of the involved species to each other.
 - Add the protective properties of corrosion products, if observed in experiments. An example could be to make the amount of precipitated product inhibit metal oxidation.

The model will be used to simulate critical corrosion phases of outdoor exposure (field and vehicle exposure) and accelerated corrosion tests in the aim of understanding the discrepancy obtained between the various exposure conditions.

In a second step, the model will be applied for more complex situation, including more layer compositions and geometrical shapes of the cut edges or damages in the steel coating. The hydrogen evolution reactions in the electrolyte layer and the kinetic of hydrogen entry into the steel will be implemented. Then, a simplification of the model will be performed based on a parametric study. Only significant quantity of hydrogen based on hydrogen embrittlement investigations will be considered. Thus, some minor variables could be averaged or even neglected in the model and the impact on the calculation results will be quantified. This way, an optimized version of the model should be produced to calculate local hydrogen entry into the steel as a function of environmental conditions

As evident from the state of the art, hydrogen embrittlement is linked to local stress, microstructure (including straining) and local hydrogen content. Several models exist to evaluate the concentration of hydrogen as a function of plastic deformation and hydrostatic stress for instance [46–48]. Even some simulation methods were built taking into account the microstructure using crystalline plasticity models. However, the activity of hydrogen controls the final concentration in the material and particularly at the crack tip. Thus, a predictive model of hydrogen assisted cracking under atmospheric corrosion conditions must be based on the external hydrogen activity. The model to be developed during this project aims at describing local hydrogen content in the bulk material as a function of

mechanical loading and external corrosion activity. The numerical model of hydrogen distribution in strain/stress field will be implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics® using existing model based on McNabb and Foster [42]. The model parameters will be adapted to the investigated steels, including trapping energies, evolution of trap density with plastic deformation and other parameters obtained experimentally. A criterion based on local hydrogen content and local stress will be established using both the simulation method and dedicated stress corrosion cracking tests. Such criterion will give practical data to the automotive industry.

4. Innovative content

A strong link will be built between coating nature (composition, morphology...), global and local corrosion conditions and hydrogen entry into high strength steels, which will give new insight into the mechanisms of hydrogen assisted cracking under atmospheric corrosion conditions. From the state of the art, no simulation method has been successfully developed up to date to link atmospheric corrosion, material composition, hydrogen entry and hydrogen distribution in steels. Results from this project would be a clear breakthrough the capability to anticipate hydrogen assisted cracking risks under atmospheric corrosion conditions for very high strength steels, raising the novelty and impact of this project.

The simulation method will be based on a commercial software, which is already largely spread in academic and industrial research centers, with a very active community and so “easy to use”. As the models will be made available through application files at the end of the project, which is not so usual in the scientific community, the method will be rapidly applicable at a large scale, enhancing its wider use. Applicability of the concept is not limited to automotive industry as atmospheric corrosion and high strength steels are present in various other industrial sectors including construction & building, marine and energy, and this clearly has an impact over the steel industry and other industrial related sectors.

To conclude, the current project addresses several topics related to the limit of use of ultra-high strength steels in the automotive industry. The gathered knowledge and the new data sets and models will represent a clear progress beyond the state of the art in all aspects related to atmospheric corrosion, hydrogen entry and hydrogen assisted cracking risks of such steels. The way how the different aspects will be interlinked is definitely an innovative concept of high relevance for the steel industry.

5. References

- [1] P.K. Mallick, Designing lightweight vehicle body, in: *Mater. Des. Manuf. Light. Veh.*, Elsevier, 2021: pp. 405–432.
- [2] M. Tisza, I. Czinege, Comparative study of the application of steels and aluminium in lightweight production of automotive parts, *Int. J. Light. Mater. Manuf.* 1 (2018) 229–238.
- [3] F. Del Pero, L. Berzi, A. Antonacci, M. Delogu, Automotive Lightweight Design: Simulation Modeling of Mass-Related Consumption for Electric Vehicles, *Machines.* 8 (2020) 51.
- [4] N. Rössler, B. Hammer, T. Heller, I. Thomas, Y. Toji, S. Takagi, K. Hasegawa, K. Seto, Evaluation of hydrogen embrittlement for ultra high strength steel sheets, in: *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Steels Cars Truck. SCT2011*, Salzburg, Austria, 2011: pp. 503–511.
- [5] D. Rudomilova, T. Prosek, G. Luckeneder, Techniques for investigation of hydrogen embrittlement of advanced high strength steels, *Corros Rev.* (2018).
- [6] M. Loidl, O. Kolk, S. Veith, T. Göbel, Characterization of hydrogen embrittlement in automotive advanced high strength steels, *Materwiss. Werksttech.* 42 (2011) 1105–1110.
- [7] J. Venezuela, F.Y. Lim, L. Liu, S. James, Q. Zhou, R. Knibbe, M. Zhang, H. Li, F. Dong, M.S. Dargusch, A. Atrens, Hydrogen embrittlement of an automotive 1700 MPa martensitic advanced high-strength steel,

- Corros. Sci. 171 (2020) 108726.
- [8] M. Wang, E. Akiyama, K. Tsuzaki, Determination of the critical hydrogen concentration for delayed fracture of high strength steel by constant load test and numerical calculation, *Corros. Sci.* 48 (2006) 2189–2202.
- [9] H.-J. Kim, M.-G. Lee, S.-C. Yoon, F. Vucko, C.-W. Lee, D. Thierry, S.-J. Kim, Diffusible hydrogen behavior and delayed fracture of cold rolled martensitic steel in consideration of automotive manufacturing process and vehicle service environment, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 9 (2020).
- [10] G. Schmitt, T. Gommlich, K. Schoettler, Electroplating of high strength steels - Hydrogen trapped in the coating endangers the base material, in: *EUROCORR 2017*, 2017: pp. 1–13.
- [11] H. Li, J. Venezuela, Z. Qian, Q. Zhou, Z. Shi, M. Yan, R. Knibbe, M. Zhang, F. Dong, A. Atrens, Hydrogen fracture maps for sheared-edge-controlled hydrogen-delayed fracture of 1180 MPa advanced high-strength steels, *Corros. Sci.* 184 (2021) 109360.
- [12] S. Ootsuka, S. Fujita, E. Tada, A. Nishikata, T. Tsuru, Evaluation of hydrogen absorption into steel in automobile moving environments, *Corros. Sci.* 98 (2015) 430–437.
- [13] S. Ajito, E. Tada, A. Ooi, A. Nishikata, Simultaneous Measurements of Corrosion Potential and Hydrogen Permeation Current in Atmospheric Corrosion of Steel, *ISIJ Int.* 59 (2019) 1659–1666.
- [14] D. Rudomilova, T. Prošek, M. Ström, Hydrogen Entry into Steel Under Corrosion Products, *Corrosion*. 77 (2021) 427–432.
- [15] A. Nazarov, F. Vucko, D. Thierry, Scanning Kelvin Probe for detection of the hydrogen induced by atmospheric corrosion of ultra-high strength steel, *Electrochim. Acta.* 216 (2016) 130–139.
- [16] E. Akiyama, M. Wang, S. Li, Z. Zhang, Y. Kimura, N. Uno, K. Tsuzaki, Studies of evaluation of hydrogen embrittlement property of high-strength steels with consideration of the effect of atmospheric corrosion, in: *Metall. Mater. Trans. A Phys. Metall. Mater. Sci.*, Springer US, 2013: pp. 1290–1300.
- [17] A. Nazarov, F. Vucko, D. Thierry, Hydrogen entry and distribution in Steel: assessments by different local electrochemical techniques, in: R. Branco (Ed.), *High-Strength Steel - New Trends Prod. Appl.*, Nova Science Publishers, New-York, 2018: pp. 35–60.
- [18] C. Bergmann, K. Mraczek, B. Kröger, T. Sturel, J. Jürgensen, Y. Yagodzinskyy, X. Guo, F. Vucko, M. Kuhlmann, S. Veith, M. Pohl, Hydrogen embrittlement resistance evaluation of advanced high strength steels in automotive applications, in: *SteelyHydrogen*, Ghent, Belgium, 2018.
- [19] Y. Kim, Y.J. Chao, M.J. Pechersky, M.J. Morgan, On the effect of hydrogen on the fracture toughness of steel, *Int. J. Fract.* 134 (2005) 339–347.
- [20] A. Alvaro, D. Wan, V. Olden, A. Barnoush, Hydrogen enhanced fatigue crack growth rates in a ferritic Fe-3 wt%Si alloy and a X70 pipeline steel, *Eng. Fract. Mech.* 219 (2019) 106641.
- [21] S. Takagi, Y. Toji, K. Hasegawa, Y. Tanaka, Hydrogen Embrittlement Evaluation Methods for Ultra-high Strength Steel Sheets for Automobiles, *Int. J. Automot. Eng.* 2 (2010) 7–13.
- [22] A.P. Nazarov, D. Thierry, Probing the atmospheric corrosion of metals. Zinc, *Prot. Met.* 42 (2006) 437–451.
- [23] N. LeBozec, D. Thierry, M. Rohwerder, D. Persson, G. Luckeneder, L. Luxem, Effect of carbon dioxide on the atmospheric corrosion of Zn-Mg-Al coated steel, *Corros. Sci.* 74 (2013) 379–386.
- [24] T. Prošek, D. Persson, J. Stouilil, D. Thierry, Composition of corrosion products formed on Zn-Mg, Zn-Al and Zn-Al-Mg coatings in model atmospheric conditions, *Corros. Sci.* 86 (2014) 231–238.

-
- [25] C. Nicard, C. Allély, P. Volovitch, Effect of Zn and Mg alloying on microstructure and anticorrosion mechanisms of Al-Si based coatings for high strength steel, *Corros. Sci.* 146 (2019) 192–201.
- [26] S.O. Kim, W.S. Yang, S.J. Kim, Effects of the Combined Addition of Zn and Mg on Corrosion Behaviors of Electropainted AlSi-Based Metallic Coatings Used for Hot-Stamping Steel Sheets, *Materials (Basel)*. 13 (2020) 3379.
- [27] O. Dolgikh, H. Simillion, N. Van Den Steen, J. Deconinck, Steps towards atmospheric corrosion modelling, *Chem. Eng. Trans.* 41 (2014) 283–288.
- [28] H. Simillion, O. Dolgikh, H. Terryn, J. Deconinck, Atmospheric corrosion: A review focussed on modelling, *Corros. Rev.* 32 (2014) 1–43.
- [29] T.E. Graedel, GILDES model studies of aqueous chemistry. I. Formulation and potential applications of the multi-regime model, *Corros. Sci.* 38 (1996) 2153–2180.
- [30] H. Gil, C. Leygraf, J. Tidblad, GILDES model simulations of the atmospheric corrosion of zinc induced by low concentrations of carboxylic acids, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 159 (2012) C123–C128.
- [31] S.P. White, G.J. Weir, N.J. Laycock, Calculating chemical concentrations during initiation of crevice corrosion, *Corros. Sci.* 42 (2000) 605–609.
- [32] F. Thebault, B. Vuillemin, R. Oltra, K. Ogle, C. Allely, Investigation of self-healing mechanism on galvanized steels cut edges by coupling SVET and numerical modeling, *Electrochim. Acta.* 53 (2008) 5226–5234.
- [33] O. Guseva, P. Schmutz, T. Suter, O. von Trzebiatowski, Modelling of anodic dissolution of pure aluminium in sodium chloride, *Electrochim. Acta.* 45 (2009) 4515–4524.
- [34] J. Xiao, S. Chaudhuri, Predictive modeling of localized corrosion: An application to aluminum alloys, *Electrochim. Acta.* 56 (2011) 5630–5641.
- [35] Y. Wang, L. Yin, Y. Jin, J. Pan, C. Leygraf, Numerical Simulation of Micro-Galvanic Corrosion in Al Alloys: Steric Hindrance Effect of Corrosion Product, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 164 (2017) C1035–C1043.
- [36] S.R. Cross, S. Gollapudi, C.A. Schuh, Validated numerical modeling of galvanic corrosion of zinc and aluminum coatings, *Corros. Sci.* 88 (2014) 226–233.
- [37] L. Yin, Y. Jin, C. Leygraf, J. Pan, A FEM model for investigation of micro-galvanic corrosion of Al alloys and effects of deposition of corrosion products, *Electrochim. Acta.* 192 (2016) 310–318.
- [38] J. Deconinck, O. Dolgikh, K. Van den Bergh, C. Allély, A. Bastos, A. Oliveira, M. Zheludkevich, M. Ferreira, S. Lamaka, B. Van Den Bossche, Modelling of atmospheric corrosion of steel protected by aluminium based alloys, applied by hot dip processing - ATCORAS - RFSR-CT-2011-00015, 2014.
- [39] E. Akiyama, S. Li, T. Shinohara, Z. Zhang, K. Tsuzaki, Hydrogen entry into Fe and high strength steels under simulated atmospheric corrosion, *Electrochim. Acta.* 56 (2011) 1799–1805.
- [40] D. Rudomilova, T. Prošek, P. Salvetr, A. Knaislová, P. Novák, R. Kodým, G. Schimo-Aichhorn, A. Muhr, H. Duchaczek, G. Luckeneder, The effect of microstructure on hydrogen permeability of high strength steels, *Mater. Corros.* 71 (2020) 909–917.
- [41] M. Nagumo, M. Nakamura, K. Takai, Hydrogen thermal desorption relevant to delayed-fracture susceptibility of high-strength steels, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* 32 (2001) 339–347.
- [42] A. McNabb, P. Foster, A new analysis of the diffusion of hydrogen in iron and ferritic steels, *Trans Met. Soc AIME.* 227 (1963) 618–627.
- [43] D. Rudomilova, T. Petrek, T. Prošek, V. Šefl, H. Duchaczek, F. Zwettler, A. Muhr, G. Luckeneder,
-

-
- Comparative study of devices for hydrogen permeation measurements, *Mater. Corros.* 69 (2018) 1398–1402.
- [44] J. Leblond, D. Dubois, A general mathematical description of hydrogen diffusion in steels—I. Derivation of diffusion equations from Boltzmann-type transport equations, *Acta Metall.* 31 (1983) 1459–1469.
- [45] R.A. Oriani, P.H. Josephic, Equilibrium aspects of hydrogen-induced cracking of steels, *Acta Metall.* 22 (1974) 1065–1074.
- [46] P. Sofronis, R.M. McMeeking, Numerical analysis of hydrogen transport near a blunting crack tip, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids.* 37 (1989) 317–350.
- [47] A. Krom, R. Koers, A. Bakker, Hydrogen transport near a blunting crack tip, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids.* (1999) 860–881.
- [48] Y. Charles, H.T. Nguyen, M. Gaspérini, FE simulation of the influence of plastic strain on hydrogen distribution during an U-bend test, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 120 (2017) 214–224.
- [49] A. Knaislova, D. Rudomilova, P. Novák, T. Prošek, A. Michalcová, P. Beran, Critical assessment of techniques for description of phase composition of advanced high strength steels, *Materials (Basel)*. 12 (2019) 4033–4046.
- [50] R. Autengruber, G. Luckeneder, A.W. Hassel, Corrosion of press-hardened galvanized steel, *Corros. Sci.* 63 (2012) 12–19.
- [51] M. Taryba, S. Lamaka, F. Montemor, Spatially resolved electrochemical tools: micropotentiometry and scanning vibrating electrode technique to detail localized corrosion problems in coated parts, in: *Handb. Mod. Coat. Technol.*, Elsevier, 2021: pp. 437–468.
- [52] A. Alvarez-Pampliega, M.G. Taryba, K. Van den Bergh, J. De Strycker, S.V. Lamaka, H. Terryn, Study of local Na⁺ and Cl⁻ distributions during the cut-edge corrosion of aluminum rich metal-coated steel by scanning vibrating electrode and micro-potentiometric techniques, *Electrochim. Acta.* 102 (2013) 319–327.
- [53] F.J. Recio, M.C. Alonso, L. Gaillet, M. Sánchez, Hydrogen embrittlement risk of high strength galvanized steel in contact with alkaline media, *Corros. Sci.* 53 (2011) 2853–2860.
- [54] N. Fujimoto, T. Sawada, E. Tada, A. Nishikata, Effect of pH on Hydrogen Absorption into Steel in Neutral and Alkaline Solutions, *Mater. Trans.* 58 (2017) 211–217.
- [55] M. Stratmann, H. Streckel, On the atmospheric corrosion of metals which are covered with thin electrolyte layers—I. Verification of the experimental technique, *Corros. Sci.* 30 (1990) 681–696.